

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS IN COGNITIVE ASPECT

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Abstract. *The fact that language plays a significant role in how humanity develops its culture and worldview is a harm to humanity. Each person reflects the process of self-realization and reflection with the aid of words. The adage "If you want to destroy a people, start with their language and culture" is well known to us from history. One can observe that language is a reflection of culture and the advancement of this people from the definition that states that language is an indistinct indicator of every Ethnos. This article keeps opinions and observations on the cognitive element of the comparative study of phraseological units.*

Keywords: *linguistics, phraseological, units, aspect, cognitive, comparative, analysis, concept, concert.*

СОПОСТАВИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМОВ В КОГНИТИВНОМ АСПЕКТЕ

Аннотация. *Тот факт, что язык играет существенную роль в том, как человечество развивает свою культуру и мировоззрение, является вредом для человечества. Каждый человек отражает процесс самореализации и рефлексии с помощью слова. Поговорка «Хочешь уничтожить народ, начни с его языка и культуры» хорошо известна нам из истории. О том, что язык является отражением культуры и развития этого народа, можно судить из определения, что язык является самостоятельным показателем каждого этноса. В данной статье собраны мнения и наблюдения по поводу познавательного элемента сопоставительного изучения фразеологических единиц.*

Ключевые слова: *языкознание, фразеологические единицы, аспект, познавательный, сравнительный, анализ, концепт, концерт.*

INTRODUCTION

By the 20th and 21st centuries, anthropocentric viewpoints in modern linguistics had solidified, and numerous new linguistic topics and branches had emerged. The cognitive study of language is one of them. Cognitive linguistics (English cognize-know, understand, understand) is a rigorous scientific study of the intimate relationship between language and thinking, linking psychological, biological, and neuro physiological aspects of its formation with social, cultural, and linguistic phenomena. It is not just concerned with the philosophy of cognition's theory of cognition. Cognitive linguistics studies the psychological notion and concept units. Meaning and image are based on the concept of concept. Cognitive linguistics is a component of the science of cognitive which in 1956 is described as follows, the problem of lexical-semantic interpretation of language units, which is associated with the human mind and vision, expressing feelings, is one of the most priority areas in the world in World linguistics, "which seeks answers to questions and observations on the means of the artificial intelligence system.

Cognitive linguistics is one of the "young" areas of linguistics, the Russian linguist E.S. Kubryakova wrote that the concept of "cognitive" came from psychology, which translates into

Russian in the sense of "relating to cognition", A.P. Babushkin noted that "cognitology is a science that has arisen at the intersection of various branches of Science, "and it was written that its field of study should be defined as the study of methods for collecting, applying knowledge. American Scientists Ronald Langaker, and Ray Djekendoff were the ones who, with their research, caused its development. Hence, a special place in the emergence of cognitive linguistics is occupied by the human mind, knowledge of the world, reflection and thinking of reality. The basis of cognitive linguistics is considered a concept, it was formed as a science in the mid-70s of the XX century, or rather, it is officially introduced in 1989 at the International Symposium of linguists in Germany. Until now, many monographs, research works have been created about cognitive linguistics, although scientific research has been carried out, but in the form of the Uzbek language is still one of the most relevant issues.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The philosopher S. Many cognitive sources included in the scientific circulation of 1928 by Askoldov stated that "concept is the word *conceptus* in Latin-"concept"" in the first part of the XX century. While Kubryakova contends that the concept is a linguistic consciousness that reflects in the human psyche and represents the image of the entire universe, another linguist, Lyapin, claims that the concept is a "multidisciplinary idealized form." The mental lexicon is regarded as an operational meaningful unit in memory. In the human spiritual realm, the thought serves as the primary unit of culture. They are the focus of emotions, loves and dislikes, and occasionally disputes. S Stepanov gave past. As can be seen from the above points, so far no cognitive definition has been given and is in the process of learning. We, both based on these points, believe that the concept is both general and individual, and each person is a concept that follows the world, his feelings, the task, based on his personal mental world. Analyzing and studying the concept, linguists divide it into different parts. In particular, Stepanov divided the concept structure into 3 parts:

1. main (aktual) character;
2. additional or passive sign;
3. internal form.

According to him, the last sign will stand in for the essential component of the ideas currently in use because there won't be anything on the side of the relationship with the first form. Let's look at some definitions from other scientists as examples: G.G. Slisshkin proposed a concept that deviated from the definition above by examining it into four zones, namely: a) the main zone - intrazona and extrazona; an additional zone - quasizona and quasiextrazonas. Popov and Sternins divided it into two (nuclear zones and peripheral zones) and explained that their mutual proportionality gives the concept a concept structure. In linguistics, the concept is seen as a linguocognitive and linguocultural phenomenon. To study the concept, it is necessary to study the worldview, living conditions and mentality, traditions of a particular nation, determine and analyze exactly the place where it occupies that concept.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is common knowledge that phraseology is the area of linguistics that deals with expressions. If we use the language of linguistic terms, phrases are phraseologisms. Phraseologism, which meaning frasis-phrase, logos-concept, doctrine, is taken from the ancient Greek language. It is necessary to take into consideration the phraseological norm, among other norms of the literary language, in order to define phraseologism as a discrete level-specific unit that

differs from the lexical-semantic and syntactic levels of a language. That is why it is accepted practice in linguistics all across the world to even record phraseologism's in explanatory dictionaries.

The study of phraseological units' semantic and structural characteristics, as well as the reasons for their emergence in the language system and the characteristics of how they are used in speech, are all covered within the particular discipline of language science known as phraseology. Phrasal and logos, two Greek terms meaning "expression, figure of speech," are combined to make the word "phraseology." Phraseology examines a language's phraseological structure in a manner similar to how lexicology examines a language's vocabulary. A phraseological unit, also known as a phraseological unit or phraseological unit, is the same linguistic unit as a word in a language's lexical system.

When determining the phraseology's object, there are many theories to consider. Only stable compounds can form the object of phraseology. According to its definition, phraseology is the study of the spiritual structural characteristics of phraseological units, as well as their appearance in the language system and application to defects. The highest level of linguistic knowledge, phraseology, provides a precise explanation of how language and culture interact. Phraseology has its own internal structure and has been established as a distinct field of linguistics with research difficulties, despite the fact that acknowledgment of phraseology as a separate science passed through various stages. Current phraseological concerns are explored one after another in modern linguistics, despite the fact that many of its problems have not yet found solutions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the richness of the Uzbek language's phraseology is the subject of some notable research. Folk dialects and the growth and expansion of the vocabulary of the literary language are intricately linked. Literary language norms are based on the lexical, phonological, and grammatical characteristics of folk dialects and are developed according to specified patterns. Therefore, one of the factors influencing the development of the contemporary Uzbek literary language and its means of becoming rich will also be the study of portable meaningful phrases in folk dialects of the national language.

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